
**USE OF SOCIAL NETWORKING SITE TOOLS FOR PROVIDING
INFORMATION SERVICES TO PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES
(DIVYANGJAN)**

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Abstract:

Nowadays, social networking site skills have become an essential tool for every learner for Information sources and services. The study focused on identifying the use patterns of information sources and services to know persons with disabilities (PWD) Divyangjan User's students' ability to identify various types and formats of potential information sources in their academic curriculum. The researcher has discussed in this article whether it can provide library services to the disabled with the help of social media. Social networking tools covered in this article are academic, information social networking tools covered in this article are academic, information transportable, and Audio- Video data transportable. Social media is used by all disabled people, just like ordinary citizens. It is suggested how educational information can be conveyed using social media and social networking.

Keywords: *Social Networking Sites, Social Networking Tools, Information Services, and Persons with disabilities (PwD) Divyangjan.*

Introduction:

Due to physical disability, a disabled person cannot visit libraries every time to get the information he needs. People with disabilities face many problems due to physical disabilities. People with disabilities must rely on an assistant to reach a particular place. Travelling is also a significant problem for the disabled. Because of this, they must sit in one place. It includes disabled people from all sections of society. Disabled people who have been determined to enter the education sector face many problems and complete their education. People with disabilities in education need different

types of information. The library is the primary source of information in the academic field. Through the library, users can get the information they need. All the services offered to students by the library must be available to every reader enrolled in that institution. By knowing the services provided by the library and the problems faced by disabled students every time they come to the library, the library must change the means of delivering their services.

Currently, information marketing and information centres are seen using social networking tools. Mainly Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, MySpace,

LinkedIn, Blogs, Instant Messaging, Wikipedia, RSS Feeds, Academic Social Networking sites (ResearchGate, Academia.edu, Google Scholar, Mendeley, and Zotero) etc. All these social networking tools can make library services easily accessible to disabled people so that disabled people get the information they want immediately.

1. Meaning and Definition of Social Networking Tools: According to Boyd and Ellison, Social Networking Sites tools as web-based services that allow individuals to:

- i. Create public or semi-public profiles within a limited system.
- ii. Determine a list of other users with whom they share connections.
- iii. View and traverse the list of links made by them and others in the system.

The nature and nomenclature of these connections may vary from site to site.

The term ‘social networking site’ is also used in public discourse to describe this phenomenon, and the two terms are often used interchangeably. ‘Networking’ often emphasises starting relationships between strangers.³

2. Information Services:

Information services promote in anticipation of the various needs of the users of libraries. At times, these services are provided on demand by the users. Information services offered by the libraries and information centres vary depending upon the library type, resources, and staff strength. Current awareness services, Circulation services, Documentation services, Inter-Library Loan, Reference services, Library Orientation, Assistance in the Use of Library and Library Tools, Condensation Services, Literature Search and Compiling a Subject Bibliography, Reprographic services, Document Delivery services,

Reader Advisory services, Translation services, Referral services, User Training, Information Technology (IT) Related Services, etc. fall under information services.

Web-based or Internet-based Services - Advances in information and communication technology and widespread use of the Internet by users have raised the demand for the provision of Web-based services by libraries. Some of the services offered under this category are: Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), Library Website, Virtual Reference Service, Computerized Circulation Service, Access to e-Publications, Access to Databases, Access to courseware, CD – ROM, RSS Feeds, Blogs, Wiki, etc.

3. Information needs for Persons with Disabilities (Divyangjan):

According to the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPwD) Act, 2016, enacted on 28.12.2016 and came into force on 19.04.2017, Disability has been considered an evolving and dynamic concept. Disabilities covered under the Act: The types of disabilities have been increased from existing 7 (as defined in the Person with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act, 1995) to 21, and the Central Government will have the power to add more types of disabilities.

The Act covers the following specified disabilities: i Blindness ii. Low-vision iii. Leprosy Cured persons iv. Hearing Impairment (deaf and hard of hearing) v. Locomotor Disability vi. Dwarfism vii. Intellectual Disability viii. Mental Illness ix. Autism Spectrum Disorder x. Cerebral Palsy xi. Muscular Dystrophy xii. Chronic Neurological conditions xiii. Specific Learning Disabilities xiv. Multiple Sclerosis xv.

Speech and Language disability xvi. Thalassaemia xvii. Haemophilia xviii. Sickle Cell disease xix. Multiple Disabilities including deaf-blindness xx. Acid Attack victims xxi. Parkinson's disease. (Source: Persons with Disabilities (Divyangjan) in India - A Statistical Profile: 2021).

Today, most of the disabled are pursuing education in the higher education sector. Students with disabilities choose subjects according to their interests. Even though students with disabilities are enrolled in different faculties, they need subject-specific information. A library is a place to meet the need for information in the field of education. The library works to fulfil the information needs of all types of students. The information needs of students with disabilities are like those of other students. But due to physical disability, they cannot go to the library every time to get the necessary information. Many times, students with physical disabilities choose subjects that are easier for them. Hence its information needs are also limited. Since the information needs of students with disabilities are rudimentary, they can be met by academic libraries. In the college where the students take admission, the books and other reading materials related to the subject taught are in the library so that they can fulfil the information needs of such students. As students with disabilities may not visit the library frequently, libraries should make efforts to promote their services through social networking. Libraries should create their accounts on various social networking tools and use them to provide information.⁴

Significance of the Study:

This study is essential for Academic libraries and Persons with *Sangram A. Killedar and Nagu N. Bansode*

disabilities (PwD) Divyangjan Users. Many online information sources are available on Social Networking Sites. Many students, teachers, and researchers also use the Social Networking Sites facility for information sources and services. Social Networking Sites are used in library and information science in various areas. Nowadays, social networking site skills have become essential for every student to access information resources and services. Social networking tools have become crucial platforms for information exchange, where people with disabilities can easily acquire information. Such platforms place collaborative learning, social learning, and value cocreation practices between organisations and their patrons.⁵

The purpose of the study is to assess Divyangjan perception of the availability of Information sources and services and the hindrances to the provision of e-resources services in academic libraries that assist with social networking tools. The specific objectives are to assess the availability of Information sources and services facilities to provide e-resources services through Social Networking Tools.

Statement of the Problem:

The researchers have the problem undertaken for the present research study entitled "Use of Social Networking tools for providing Information Services to Person with Disability (Divyangjan)."

Review of Literature:

Midhula & Sudhier (2015) highlighted the ability to identify patterns in the various types and formats of potential information sources and services in educational curricula for persons with disabilities (PWD) students. This study reminds us that the basic needs of students

with disabilities are not unique but fundamental. Through increased involvement and participation in promoting the inclusion of children with different abilities, technology can reduce the effects of disability. The study found that none of the students had sufficient confidence in using assistive technology and online resources. The author opined that school administrations should make efforts to provide Internet resources and assistive technology to visually impaired students.⁹

Raja (2016) noted that people with disabilities are excluded or marginalised, which affects their countries' human rights and economies. Digital technologies have reduced, if not eliminated, traditional barriers to communication, interaction, and access to information for people with disabilities. A technology-enabled development model for people with disabilities is becoming mainstream. This is changing daily due to the increasing number of ICTs that can be used as accessible tools and the expansion of public and professional service provision through ICT. According to a report, accessible ICT can level the playing field for people with disabilities in areas such as education, employment, e-government, civic participation, financial inclusion, and disaster preparedness in their lives.¹¹

Wang, Wu et al. (2017) highlighted the problem of combining information delivery with Internet technology for people with disabilities. Improving their quality of life is impossible if their unique needs are ignored. This study used crowdsourcing through social media methods to investigate the information needs of people with disabilities. The study reveals that using the popular social

media platform, WeChat effectively reaches out to this group.¹⁵

Ayoung, Baada, & Baayel (2020) have studied the challenges that hinder persons with disabilities from accessing reliable information from academic libraries. Respondents were purposively selected from 11 tertiary institutions, most of which were visually or mobility impaired, and their interviews provided the data for analysis. The results also show that library staff members are not sufficiently knowledgeable about the problems of people with disabilities and their right to information. This study thus suggests that it should empower appropriate state agencies to implement the Disability Act with Ghanaians and better inform stakeholders on the need to increase access to information by persons with disabilities.²

Abutayeh and Garcia-Orosa (2021) shifted from a library information management approach to a user-centred/content management approach in less than a century. Technology is constantly evolving to make finding and accessing information as easy as possible. The growing demand for information among university students, especially vulnerable users, supports the need for more effective, game-changing, self-learning tools in libraries and new technological advances to redefine the profession and move away from low-level management. This study contributes to librarianship by discussing topics available for further research; these findings will interest library managers, administrators, librarians, and scholars.¹

Odigie, Imoisili, Okube, and Nwakaego (2021) observed that learning difficulties prevent students with disabilities from fully benefiting from their educational programmes. The study's objective was to

understand assistive technology's presence and function in libraries in Kogi State. Some assistive technologies, such as computers and LCD projectors, were the focus of research, but most assistive technologies were unavailable in institutions. This study presents some assistive technology functions to provide equal opportunities and library services to the users of these technologies. The author believed that librarians should be taught how to use technology through teacher workshops because it would better prepare them to instruct users.¹⁰

Objectives of the study:

The present research has taken up the following objectives:

- To discover what information services are provided to Persons with Disabilities (Divyangjan) users in academic libraries.
- To investigate the dimensions and use of Information resources, assistive technologies, and communication mediums for Persons with Disabilities (PwD).

- To know how to use library resources and services for Persons with Disabilities (Divyangjan) through social networking tools.
- To Identify which library services can be provided to persons with disabilities by adopting new technological tools such as social networking sites.

Social Networking Tools and their use for PwD (Divyangjan):

According to Dr. S. R. Ranganathan's 2nd law of Library and Information Science brings Persons with Disabilities (Divyangjan) students into the ambit of public libraries. The Tremendous popularity of social networking tools presents libraries with unique opportunities for reaching Divyangjan students. Social networking is crucial for our academic and learning endeavours. The use of social networking tools makes an impact on our learning and extension tasks. There are three main types of Social Networking Tools: Communication Tools, Knowledge Organisation Tools, and Information Distribution tools.¹²

Sr. No	Social Networking Tools	Functions of Social Networking Tools	Use for PwD (Divyangjan)
	Communication Tools	In the Digital era, the librarian can be Supportive in keeping in touch and effective interaction with staff and users in an online collaborative environment.	
1.	Blog	Creating a blog allows you to disseminate information to many people at once. A short weblog is a frequently updated website about a particular topic that contains dated entries in reverse chronological order.	Blogs are a powerful tool for PwD students to update on new collections and converse with library staff.
2.	Facebook	The main objective of Facebook is entertainment. Every registered user has an individual profile who can make friends, send messages, upload photos, videos, likes, comments, share links and resources, and update their profile.	Libraries should create their own Facebook page and share its link with PwD students. The library should update the students about the library by sharing information of general interest like new arrivals, library notifications, news and events, and library

			orientation videos through the Facebook page. ¹⁴
3.	MySpace	MySpace primarily has a social function allowing people to make friends, talk online, and share resources.	Libraries have taken advantage of these sites for providing 'Ask A Librarian' service, Catalogue search tools, and sharing ideas and resources with PwD Users.
4.	Meebo	Meebo has an instant messaging and social networking service provider.	Professionals can impact clients' virtual reference services in the library.
5.	Ning	NING is the world's largest store of social networking expertise for innovative online communication communities. NING sites are capable and feature fast hosting, in-depth analytics, and advanced monetisation options.	Librarians can use this tool to connect with students, Academic library associations, and more. It uses to share information with PwD Users.
6.	Twitter	Twitter is a microblogging and social networking service on which users post. Users access Twitter through its website interface, Short Message Service (SMS), or mobile-device application software.	Interact to keep staff and patrons updated on daily activities, like frequently updated collections, new arrival, and current content services of the library.
7.	LinkedIn	LinkedIn is a business and employment-oriented online service. LinkedIn can also be used to organise offline events, join groups, write articles, publish job postings, post photos and videos, and more.	This social networking site for professionals is a great way to connect library patrons with people who can help them find information.
8.	WhatsApp	WhatsApp Messenger is a freeware online messaging and Voice over IP (VoIP) service owned by Facebook. Users could communicate with individuals or informal groups on WhatsApp.	WhatsApp allows users to send text messages and voice recordings, make voice and video calls and share images, documents, user locations, and other media.
9.	Instant Messaging (IM)	It is real-time communication between two or more people based on typed text. The text is conveyed through a computer connected over a network such as an internet. Instant Messaging is a form of real-time direct text-based communication between two or more online people simultaneously.	Providing virtual reference service, integrating vendor's answers to queries, Providing instant messages about library-related news, Provide the new arrivals based on the subject interest.
10.	WeChat	WeChat is a messaging social media app developed by Tencent. User activity on WeChat is used for mass surveillance.	Library uses these tools for messaging several users at the same time.

Knowledge / Organisation tools		Social software can help the professionals in the environment get handy information accessible with the social networking technologies in web 2.0. The below-mentioned tools cab effectively in library and information centres for patrons as:	
1.	LibraryThing	This social cataloguing network is excellent for librarian's catalogues along with Amazon, the Library of Congress, and more than 300 other libraries worldwide. You'll get recommendations and easy tagging as well.	PWD students are provided with a bibliographic catalogue of the library through these tools, which students can select the book they want and request it from the library. There will be no need to visit the library and search the entire shelves to choose a book.
2.	Del.icio.us	Delicious was a social bookmarking web service for storing, sharing, and discovering web bookmarks.	This social bookmarking tool can create a custom directory for library patrons. Teach them to search by your tags, and it will be easy to find helpful Internet research links.
3.	Lib.rario.us	Built started it on top of a sort of custom framework that had been built with a small library of everyday routines.	On another social cataloguing site, you can put media such as books, CDs, and journals on display for easy access and tracking.
4.	Connotea	Connote a is a great reference tool, allowing you to save and organise reference links and share them with others. They can be accessed from any computer and offer integration with many other devices.	Librarians, Staff, and researchers use this to create references. Allowing you to link, manage and save references and share them with others can be accessed from any computer so students can use them for research.
5.	aNobii	aNobii social networking allows book lovers to share reviews and suggestions. It also prepares due date alerts, lending, and discussions.	Discover new and old books, build your library, and meet millions of book lovers from around the word
6.	Netvibes	Netvibes is a French company that offers web services.	In Netvibes' you can create a public page that anyone can view. It uses it to help guide patrons to use internet sources, news feeds, and more.
Information / Distribution Tools		Information dissemination and sharing are significant and crucial areas where Academic LIS professionals should look seriously while considering and designing library activities in the modern digital age. User Satisfaction is the priority by providing the correct information at the right time in the right way.	
1.	SlideShare	Promote faculty, staff, and students to share their slideshow presentations for the greater community to access on Slide Share.	It is a great way to disseminate information among the PwD community in research.
2.	YouTube	YouTube is a video-sharing website. It allows users to upload, view, rating, share, report, add to playlists, comment on videos, and subscribe. It delivers a wide variety of user-generated and corporate media videos.	Library video and e-learning tutorials, events, and others video library services can be effectively promoted and webcast through YouTube.
3.	Flickr	It is an image distribution tool and a	The library can share a photo collection

		great way to share new image collections. You can create image sets with metadata and take advantage of the many plug-ins available for Flickr users. Flickr users can also help gather missing information about images.	of workshops, conferences, and different programmes reorganised within the campus.
4.	Wikipedia	Wikipedia is an online edited encyclopaedia. It is a multilingual, web-based free-content encyclopaedia. Wikipedia is written collaboratively by an international group of volunteers. It is a website that allows multiple users to create, modify and collaboratively organise Web content.	Share your knowledge by editing or pointing library patrons in the right direction. You can host your library websites on wiki software like PB Wiki.
5.	TeacherTube	Teacher Tube, a YouTube for teachers, presents an excellent opportunity for instructor-librarian collaboration.	Librarians can guide students to helpful resources and vice versa.
6.	Second Life	Second Life is an online multimedia platform that allows people to create an avatar for themselves and interact with other users and user-created content within a multi-player online virtual world.	You can create a virtual library on Second Life with streaming media, discussions, classes, and more.
7.	PBwiki	PBwiki is the world's largest provider of hosted business and educational wikis.	It promotes student collaboration, is a way to showcase work, and provides a central aggregation point for information.
8.	Digg	Digg is a news aggregator with a curated front page, aiming to select stories specifically for the Internet audience, such as science, trending political issues, and viral Internet issues.	Digg is a great way to find helpful content that you would not see in traditional ways. Find stories here, then share them with others using Digg's blog function.
9.	StumbleUpon	It is a discovery and advertisement engine that pushes web content recommendations to its users.	It allows users to discover and rate Web pages, photos and videos that are personalised to their tastes and interests using peer-sourcing, social networking, and advertising principles.
10.	RSS Feed	Really Simple Syndication feed is a format for delivering changing and frequently updated web content like blog entries, news headlines, audio, and video.	RSS sends timely information and updates to PwD people who subscribe to it. It helps publish Web content.
11.	Podcast	Podcasts are distributed over the internet using syndication feeds for playback on portable media players and computers.	The Divyangjan user can download and listen to serialised digital audio or video files.
12.	Instagram	Instagram is a photo, and video content communicating social networking service owned by Facebook, Inc. Users can browse other user content by tags	The app allows users to upload pictures and videos to the service, which can be edited with various filters and organised with tags and location

		and locations and view trending content.	information.
13.	Academic Social Networking (ASNs)	ASNs are more specific to academicians in sharing their activities, specialisations, publications and assessing other impacts of scholarly contribution.	Divyangjan users can use ASNs to share their research ideas and publications with the community.
14.	Social Bookmarking	It is an online service that allows users to bookmark, annotate, edit, and share web documents.	This tool can teach them to search by your tags, making it easy for library patrons to find helpful Internet links.

Conclusion:

Social networking sites are currently the most used tool in the world. Many types of information are exchanged around the world through them. With the effective use of social media, libraries can also provide all their services to the readers in the least possible time. Social networking can provide information for physically challenged people to make the information they need available at their homes or wherever they want. For this, modern libraries should use various tools, create library accounts on social networking platforms, and provide services. Social Networking tools and technologies play crucial roles for Persons with Disabilities (Divyangjan) students to reduce the barriers and access to information.

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